

Communication Plan

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Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions

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ABSTRACT

This communication plan has been prepared to ensure the regularity and quality of communication activities in the project.

This communication plan specifies activity, goal, message, target group, performing partner, language, channel and expected result. The plan will be updated regularly and has mostly focus on the external communication activities.

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1 Executive summary

This communication plan has been prepared to ensure the regularity and quality of communication activities in the project, and is intended to assist the project in achieving the following objectives:

- to promote wider uptake of smart water solutions
- to increase awareness in the society of the need and value (and existence!) of smart water solutions for sustainable development in all countries
- to contribute to removing regulatory/legal/managerial barriers by distributing evidence-based information to decision makers and politicians
- to inform about the measures identified and demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE to overcome barriers
- to inspire relevant stakeholders to spin-off projects and new demonstrations of water smart concepts.

This communication plan specifies activity, goal, message, target group, performing partner, language, channel and expected result. The plan will be updated regularly and has mostly focus on the external communication activities.

2 Objectives

2.1 Short about the project

WIDER UPTAKE is a H2020 project that aims to facilitate industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. The project's hypothesis is that the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social, and economic character.

WIDER UPTAKE will identify and demonstrate common measures to overcome barriers related to:

1. 'Monitoring and control of health and quality risks'
2. 'Circular-economy and efficiency potential'
3. 'Governance and business models for industrial symbiosis'
4. 'Measuring water smartness and progress towards SDG'.

The project includes demonstrations at five different locations/countries/settings of:

- Wastewater reuse for agriculture and urban greening
- Phosphorus recycling, biogas and biochar utilisation
- Production of biocomposites for manufacturing materials with resources recovered from the whole water cycle.

The partnership in WIDER UPTAKE includes 11 water utilities and industries and 7 research institutes or universities, distributed across 5 countries (Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy and Ghana).

2.2 Expectations from the European Commission on communication

The European Commission has clearly stated that the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results. 'Promoting the action' means providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange

Further, the Commission expects the communication activities must:

- be effective (i.e. suited to achieving the action's communication goals),
- be proportionate to the scale of the action, and
- address audiences that go beyond the action's own community (including the media and the public).

Ad hoc efforts or mere dissemination of results are NOT sufficient. Dissemination of results cannot replace communication activities (or vice-versa); both provisions must be complied with.

Moreover, the activities must make the research activities known to multiple audiences (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists) and include the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by addressing aspects such as:

- Transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible)
- Scientific excellence
- Contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges

- Impact on everyday lives (e.g. creation of jobs, development of new technologies, better quality products, more convenience, improved lifestyle, etc.)
- Better use of results and spill-over to policymakers, industry and the scientific community.

Any communication activity that is expected to have a major media impact (i.e. media coverage (online and printed press, broadcast media, social media, etc.) that will go beyond having a local impact and which could have the potential for national and international outreach) must be first notified to the Commission.

2.3 Purpose of the communication plan

This communication plan has been prepared to ensure the regularity and quality of communication activities in the project, and is intended to assist the project in achieving the following objectives:

- to promote wider uptake of smart water solutions
- to increase awareness in the society of the need and value (and existence!) of smart water solutions for sustainable development in all countries
- to contribute to removing regulatory/legal/managerial barriers by distributing evidence-based information to decision makers and politicians
- to inform about the measures identified and demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE to overcome barriers
- to inspire relevant stakeholders to spin-off projects and new demonstrations of water smart concepts.

This communication plan specifies activity, goal, message, target group, performing partner, language, channel and expected result. The plan will be updated regularly and has mostly focus on the external communication activities.

Finally, WIDER UPTAKE will monitor the impact of the communication activities by means of several performance indicators (number of people asking for feedback or more information about the project, speaker evaluations from conference presentations, number of media clips, level of activity at blog and web statistics).

3 Communication principles

The objectives of our communication activities are as follows:

- To contribute towards the projects achieving their objectives
- To make the results of projects visible
- To make the value of the projects visible to society as a whole
- To ensure that we provide knowledge and premises for public debate and policy development

We would like our communication to be characterized by:

- Active from day one of the project
- Promotes two-way engagement
- Involves all the project partners

This communication plan is based on SINTEF's communication strategy and communication model (see figure 1).

Figure 1 SINTEF's communication model

3.1 The communication model applied to WIDER UPTAKE

This section explains how the communication model in figure 1 (above) is applied for WIDER UPTAKE.

3.1.1 OBJECTIVES (Why?)

The overall goal of the communication activities is to promote wider implementation of smart water solutions. More specifically, also thinking about the expected reaction and change expected from the target audiences, the goal will be achieved through:

- Increase awareness in the society of the need and value (and existence!) of smart water solutions for sustainable development in all countries, in line with circular economy principles.
- Inform about the effect that implementation of smart water solutions will have on the daily life of citizens at local, regional and national level.
- Contribute to removing regulatory/legal/managerial barriers by distributing evidence-based information to decision makers and politicians, engage in dialogue and receive feedback, influence the attitude of decision-makers.
- Inform the right target groups about the measures identified and demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE to overcome barriers and inspire relevant industrial stakeholders to spin-off projects and new demonstrations of water smart concepts.
- Gather interest from media from the beginning of the project, to secure highest impact of the demonstrations.

3.1.2 TARGET GROUPS (Who?)

There is a variety of potential audiences for WIDER UPTAKE, but it is crucial to identify as specific as possible the prioritized targets for the project in order to achieve the communication goals of the project in an effective way and with maximum impact.

The targeted audiences for WIDER UPTAKE are:

- Citizens living in medium to large size towns, and persons living in agricultural areas.
- Politicians and decision makers at local and regional, involved in the planning of new water infrastructure in 2020-2040, and in charge of water and energy management. National politicians and decision makers involved in the implementation of circular economy concepts at regional, national and international level.
- Standardisation and regulatory bodies at national level concerned with quality of water for various applications, and composition of sludge for agricultural applications.
- Companies and investors interested in commercialization of smart water solutions and industrial symbiosis.
- Intermediary audiences that can be instrumental for further distribution of information, such as Sectoral organisations, NGOs and the Communities of practice in WIDER UPTAKE (all stakeholders linked to the project).
- The scientific community linked to the topics in WIDER UPTAKE.
- Media - both local, global and social media to enlighten and inform, to spread the news, show how important it is to work together across borders in scientific research and spread the results afterwards through success stories from the project.

In addition to the communication activities directed at the above specific target groups, the project includes some general research dissemination and promotional activities that cover several target groups.

3.1.3 CONTENT AND MESSAGE (What?)

The message to be communicated will be that smart use of water itself and other resources from water and wastewater treatment can create green industries and jobs and contribute to achieving the UN sustainable development goals. It will be of crucial importance to address the concern of the public and authorities regarding health and risk aspects linked to the re-use of treated wastewater and nutrients. Further, WIDER UPTAKE will illustrate how re-use of wastewater and recovery of nutrients are feasible applications of circular economy concepts. WIDER UPTAKE will be a living example about how different countries encounter similar problems, and working as a team, scientists and local stakeholders are finding smart solutions. Throughout the communication, WIDER UPTAKE will show how European research and innovation contributes to raising European competitiveness and to solving societal challenges.

3.1.4 MEASURES AND CHANNELS (How?)

By involving experts in communication from the different partners – representing different countries and cultures – WIDER UPTAKE will ensure that the project conducts the right communication activities, makes the right choice of channel for each target group, appropriate language, format (e.g. illustration, film, text, press release, etc.) and adequate scale. The communication activities targeting general public and politicians will use language and format that can be understood by non-specialist. The activities will be either at local, regional, national or international scale in order to address the cultural variations among the participating countries. The cultural variations might also affect the choice of channel. Depending on the target audience, some of the communication will be two ways as being able to receive feedback and interact will be important. In this context, social media channels can play an important part.

For research-oriented content, WIDER UPTAKE will make use of presentation material, website, video, fact sheets, news updates, scientific publications, media articles and press releases. In addition to communication events organized by the project, the project will focus on profiting from being present and active at existing meetings and conferences and collaborate with others to amplify our work. Further, social media will be used to certain extent for communication to the general public.

Figure 2 Illustration of channels and target groups

4 Action plan

4.1 General

Task 7.4 in Work Package 7 (Collaboration, communication and management, WP7) is dedicated to communication. In addition, there are dissemination activities planned in Work Package 6 (Roadmap for water-smartness, exploitation and dissemination in new ways for increased engagement, WP6). The task 7.4. leader, Maria Barrio (SINTEF), is responsible for ensuring that all activities described in the communication plan are carried out. SINTEF has allocated resources from its communication department to promote the project effectively and professionally. Further, internal coordination and cooperation among the communication experts in each partner is crucial to secure a coherent and swift action during the entire duration of the project and beyond.

Partners from each country in WIDER UPTAKE will take responsibility for communication events at national/regional level. Use of local language will be important in order to reach some of the targeted audiences.

4.2 External communication about the project and its results

Table 1 shows the planned communication activities for WIDER UPTAKE. Cells in yellow refer to the communication activities strongly linked to dissemination of results. More details about the dissemination of results will be provided in the Updated dissemination and exploitation plan (D6.1), due in Month 6.

Table 1: External communication activities. Cells in yellow refer to the communication activities strongly linked to dissemination of results.

Activity	Objective	Target group	Channel	Deadline/frequency	Person responsible	Assisted by
General oral presentation of the project	To release general information about the project overall content at non-technical level (English)	All target groups	PowerPoint presentation, downloadable from the website Also available as a short video at the website	Available after kick-off meeting, regularly updated with major project achievements	Task 7.4 lead	Project management team (PMT)
Country specific overall oral presentation of the project	To release general information at national level about the project overall content at non-technical level and about the demonstration cases in the country	Citizens, National, regional and local politicians and decision makers Standardisation and regulatory bodies at national level Intermediary national audiences Local media	PowerPoint presentation that can be downloadable from the partners websites in country languages.	Available after month 3, regularly updated with major project achievements.	PMT participant from each country	Task 7.4 lead
General presentation of the project in text (max. 500 words)	To release general information about the project in non-technical language (English)	All target groups	Text in pdf, downloadable from the website	Available after kick-off meeting, regularly updated with major project achievements	Task 7.4 lead	PMT and communication department
Website	Establish a main channel for open access communication, and guide audiences to the national contact points	Different pages might have different target groups. Parts of the website should be technical.	Website	Available after month 3, gradually including more information as results are produced.	Task 7.4 lead	PMT and communication department at coordinator

<p>News and events updates</p>	<p>To maintain momentum in the project, share results and gather interest from media</p> <p>Act as ONE project</p>	<p>All target groups</p>	<p>Website</p>	<p>To generate at least one news item per month and at significant milestones of the project</p>	<p>Task 7.4 lead</p>	<p>Communication s Department All partners</p>
<p>Prepare communication material for general public</p>	<p>Increase awareness around smart water solutions</p> <p>Inform about effect of implementation</p> <p>At national and international level</p>	<p>Citizens living in medium to large size towns</p> <p>Persons living in agricultural areas. National, regional and local politicians and decision makers</p> <p>Companies and investors interested in commercialization of smart water solutions</p>	<p>Choice of channel should depend on the specific country and topic.</p> <p>Brochure, media kit, videos for web and social media, webinar/ video podcast.</p> <p>Local/national media: Media articles, press releases, chronicles</p> <p>Newspapers (online and printed), TV and radio.</p>	<p>At least one communication package per country involved in the project.</p> <p>Additional material will be produced connected to achieving major milestones in the project.</p>	<p>Case owners and PMT</p>	<p>Task WP7.4 lead</p>
<p>Policy briefs</p>	<p>Contribute to remove barriers</p> <p>Engage in dialogue and receive feedback</p> <p>Inform about measures identified and demonstrated</p> <p>Gather media interest to secure project impact</p> <p>inform about prioritized recommendations for responsible actors</p>	<p>EU, National, regional and local politicians and decision makers</p> <p>Standardisation and regulatory bodies at national level</p> <p>Policy makers</p> <p>Intermediary national audiences</p> <p>Local media</p>	<p>Choice of channel should depend on the specific country and topic.</p> <p>Policy briefs, white papers, media releases in technical magazines or specialized press.</p>	<p>At least one item per country involved in the project.</p> <p>Additional material will be produced connected to achieving major milestones in the project, in particular from WP2 and WP4.</p>	<p>Task WP7.4 lead</p>	<p>WP4 lead</p>

wider uptake

<p>Communication events mostly for stakeholders in the sector</p>	<p>Increase awareness around smart water solutions</p> <p>Inform about effect of implementation</p> <p>Contribute to remove barriers</p> <p>Inform about measures identified and demonstrated</p> <p>Inspire stakeholders to spin-off projects and actions</p> <p>Gather media interest to secure project impact</p> <p>Local/regional and national promotion of the demonstration sites</p>	<p>Companies and investors interested in commercialization of smart water solutions</p> <p>National, regional and local politicians and decision makers</p> <p>Standardisation and regulatory bodies at national level</p> <p>Policy makers</p> <p>Intermediary national audiences</p> <p>Local media</p>	<p>Info gatherings and events at the relevant location, followed by reporting the event and related documents at website and social media.</p> <p>(if physical meetings are not possible, it will be substituted by digital events)</p>	<p>At least one communication event at each demonstration site during the lifetime of the project, following the results and major achievements and milestones at the demonstration sites</p>	<p>Case owners and PMT</p>	<p>Task 7.4 lead</p>
<p>(Scientific) Publications</p>	<p>Inform the right target groups about the measures identified and demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE to overcome barriers</p> <p>Inspire relevant industrial stakeholders to spin-off projects and new demonstrations of water smart concepts.</p>	<p>Scientific community, investors and industrial stakeholders, or sectorial organisations</p>	<p>Open access publications, also available through website</p>	<p>During the lifetime of the project, following project deliverables</p>	<p>WP2-WP5 leads</p>	<p>Project partners</p>
<p>Contributions to conferences and seminars to</p>	<p>Inform the right target groups about the measures identified and demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE to overcome barriers</p>	<p>Scientific community, investors and industrial stakeholders, or sectorial organisations</p>	<p>Open access publications, also available through website</p>	<p>During the lifetime of the project, following project deliverables</p>	<p>WP2-WP5 leads</p>	<p>Project partners</p>

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inform about project results	Inspire relevant industrial stakeholders to spin-off projects and new demonstrations of water smart concepts.					
Workshops, training activities and summer schools	Dissemination and exploitation of results (WP6)	Scientific community Young researchers	Physical or digital gatherings	During the lifetime of the project, following relevant deliverables	WP6 lead	Project partners

4.3 Internal communication within WIDER UPTAKE

The following activities will be performed to ensure agile internal communication within WIDER UPTAKE, involvement of all partners and facilitate that we act as one project. Table 2 shows more details about the different activities:

Table 2 Internal communication within the project

Activity	Objective	Target group	Channel	Deadline/frequency	Person responsible
Meetings	To ensure work progress and information sharing between partners (e.g. working in the same work package, same task, same demonstration case)	Consortium partners	Digital and physical meetings	As deemed necessary	Coordinator, PMT, task leaders, case owners
Information sharing and coordination	Ensure involvement of all partners and effective communication. In particular to enable learning and mutual update on progress and status in the different demonstration cases	Consortium partners	MS Teams, official contact list, dynamic and regular use of website, e-mail	Continuously	All partners
Sharing of work documents and tools	Easy access tools for effective teamwork	Consortium partners	MS Teams, open access for publications, active use of website Virtual learning centre	Continuously	All partners
Status reporting	Comply with EU requirements and act as one project	Consortium partners and EU Commission	MS Teams	According to the reporting routines of the EU Commission and as deemed necessary by the PMT	Coordinator and PMT